

Solvent hydrogen bonding and structural influences on the Cr^{VI} oxidation of anilines in aqueous acetic acid medium

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Abstract : The oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted anilines by Cr^{VI} oxidant, imidazolium fluorochromate (IFC), in aqueous acetic acid mixtures of varying compositions in the presence of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (PTS) is first order in IFC and PTS. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics is observed with all of the anilines. The IFC oxidation of 15 *meta*- and *para*-substituted anilines at 299–322 K complies with the isokinetic relationship but not to any of the linear free energy relationships. The isokinetic temperature lies within the experimental range. The rate data failed to correlate with macroscopic solvent parameters such as relative permittivity, ϵ_r , and ionizing power, Y , correlation of rate data with Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic parameters (hydrogen bond donor acidity, α , hydrogen bond acceptor basicity, β , and dipolarity/polarizability, π^*) is linear which suggests that the specific solute-solvent interactions play a dominating role in governing the reactivity.

Keywords : Aniline, kinetics, oxidation, solvent effect.

Introduction

The kinetic studies of oxidation of organic compounds in non-aqueous and aquo-organic solvent media have revealed the important role of non-specific and specific solvent effects on the reactivity. It has been shown that the reactivity is influenced by the preferential solvation of the reactants and/or the transition state through non-specific and specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions. Furthermore, it has been established that the technique of correlation analysis may well be used to separate, quantify and rationalize such solvent-solvent-solute interactions on reactivity¹⁻⁵.

Further, one of the important tools in deciding the mechanism of reactions is the study of substituent effects and thermodynamic parameters. The Hammett equation and its modified forms⁶, all known as Linear Free Energy Relationships (LFER) have been found useful for correlating reaction rates and equilibrium constants for side chain reactions for *meta*- and *para*-substituted derivatives. The isokinetic relationship is also an important tool for deciding the nature of a mechanism. Keeping this in view, a systematic study of various LFERs and the isokinetic relationship has been made to establish the role of solvent and substituents on reactivity and to decide the

nature of the mechanism being followed in the imidazolium fluorochromate (IFC, a mild and selective oxidant, reported only recently⁷) oxidation of some *meta*- and *para*-substituted anilines. This article focuses on the study of kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of substituted anilines by IFC in aqueous acetic acid mixtures of varying compositions.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade. The solid anilines were used as such and the liquid anilines were used after vacuum distillation. Imidazolium Fluorochromate (IFC) was prepared by reported method⁷ and standardized iodometrically.

Kinetic measurements : The reaction was initiated by adding IFC to the substrate. The progress of the oxidation, with aniline in large excess, was followed by iodometric estimation of the unconsumed oxidizing agent. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were determined by least squares method, from the linear plots ($r > 0.97$) of $\log [IFC]$ versus time. Replicate runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The reaction was carried out in varying mole fractions (0.3–0.9) of acetic acid in water at 26, 34, 42 and 49

(± 0.1) °C and the activation parameters were computed.

Data analysis : Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient (r in the case of simple linear regression and R in the case of multiple linear regression), standard deviation, σ , and Exner's statistical parameter, Ψ . The percentage contribution (P_x) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed using the regression coefficient of each parameter as reported earlier⁸.

Stoichiometry : The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by carrying out several sets of experiments with varying amounts of [IFC] largely in excess over [aniline]. The estimation of unreacted IFC showed that one mole of aniline reacts with one mole of IFC.

Product analysis : The oxidation product was analyzed using preparative TLC on silica gel, which yielded azobenzene m.p. 66 °C (lit. 68 °C), UV (EtOH) λ_{max} 320 nm and was confirmed using FT-IR spectra by comparing with the authentic sample.

Results and discussion

The kinetic studies were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions with the [substrate] \gg [IFC]. The first order dependence of the reaction on IFC is obvious from the linearity of the plots of \log [IFC] versus time. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , do not depend on the initial concentration of IFC (Table 1). At fixed [IFC], the rate of oxidation increases with increasing [substrate]. The plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus [substrate]⁻¹ is linear with definite intercept on the rate ordinate, which indicates the operation of Michaelis-Menten mechanism

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants ($10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$, s⁻¹) for the oxidation of aniline by IFC in aqueous acetic acid medium at 299 K

10 ² [Aniline] (M)	10 ³ [IFC] (M)	10 ³ [PTS] (M)	10 ⁴ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)
2.0	1.00	1.0	7.09
2.0	1.25	1.0	7.12
2.0	1.50	1.0	6.98
2.0	1.75	1.0	7.11
2.0	1.0	1.0	7.09
2.0	1.0	2.0	14.89
2.0	1.0	3.0	18.81
2.0	1.0	4.0	28.82
2.0	1.0	2.0	12.10 ^a

^aContained 0.001 M, Mn^{II}.

for the oxidation process. A representative plot is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Michaelis-Menten plot for the oxidation of aniline by IFC :
[IFC] = 1×10^{-3} M; [PTS] = 2×10^{-2} M.

where K is the equilibrium constant for the formation of Michaelis-Menten complex, and k the rate constant for the decomposition of Michaelis-Menten complex. Usually first step is a fast pre-equilibrium and the electron-transfer step is rate determining. The pseudo-first order rate constant reads, under [substrate] $>$ [IFC] :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{kK [\text{Substrate}]}{1 + K [\text{Substrate}]}$$

According to the above equation k and K could be separately determined just by employing different excess of the substrate and plotting k_{obs}^{-1} versus [substrate]⁻¹ and the values are given in Table 2. The oxidation of aniline by IFC was found to be catalyzed by presence of *p*-toluene sulfonic acid and the k_{obs} values varied with variation in the initial concentration of PTS (Table 1) and dependence on acid was also observed to be unity, as seen from linear plot ($r = 0.993$, $\sigma = 0.04$, $\Psi = 0.17$, slope = 0.97 ± 0.08) of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus \log [PTS]. Catalysis by *p*-toluenesulfonic acid suggests hydrolysis of the IFC spe-

Table 2. Rate constants and equilibrium constants for the oxidation of amines by IFC at 299 K

Solvent ^a	H	<i>p</i> -Me	<i>p</i> -OMe	<i>p</i> -COMe	<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	$10^5 k \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$							<i>m</i> -COMe	
							<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -F	<i>m</i> -Me	<i>m</i> -COOH	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	<i>m</i> -Et		<i>m</i> -OMe
0.3	5.9	13.1	5.3	1.0	65.7	0.17	17.9	1.1	23.7	35.8	0.48	0.31	3.6	13.7	0.52
0.4	7.7	22.3	5.5	1.5	116	0.18	25.2	1.8	25.7	37.3	0.69	0.40	4.0	25.6	0.63
0.5	10.0	43.8	8.3	1.7	145	0.19	30.8	15.4	48.4	118	0.77	0.50	5.8	34.6	1.2
0.6	32.3	373	8.7	1.9	262	0.36	36.4	17.5	132	139	1.9	0.51	8.6	46.6	3.1
0.7	40.1	481	16.8	2.4	270	0.56	133	72.6	152	186	4.6	0.86	38.5	169	3.8
0.8	219	591	37.4	5.5	553	1.6	288	180	457	478	6.5	5.6	57.5	350	6.0
0.9	1630	653	429	10.1	1130	1.9	336	452	1450	523	14.5	6.9	159	1230	22.3
							$K \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$								
0.3	183	45	93	38	28	112	56	223	29	24	112	414	135	80	92
0.4	115	32	150	20	35	371	56	168	53	24	73	167	145	62	103
0.5	97	20	121	41	19	763	65	17	40	22	72	359	116	90	53
0.6	42	4	105	39	21	260	56	33	53	47	66	473	79	95	248
0.7	93	12	37	44	26	263	83	7	63	52	47	378	54	66	138
0.8	24	22	33	20	13	360	32	1	29	45	150	32	85	50	560
0.9	10	70	3	152	11	219	28	44	16	74	62	143	49	12	81

^a*m.f.* of acetic acid in water; [Substrate] = $5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$; [IFC] = $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; [PTS] = $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$.

cies rather than the protonation of the aniline molecule, which would have resulted in rate retardation⁹. The reaction did not promote polymerization of acrylonitrile indicating absence of free radicals. However, addition of Mn^{II}, in the form of MnSO₄, retard the rate of the oxidation process indicating two electron oxidation¹⁰.

Activation parameters : The activation parameters were calculated from k at 299, 307, 315 and 322 K using the Eyring relationship by the method of least squares and are collected in Table 3. The decomposition of Michaelis-Menten complex is neither isoenthalpic nor isentropic but conforms to the compensation law also known as isokinetic relationship. The isokinetic temperature is the temperature at which all the substrates of the series react at equal rate. At the isokinetic temperature the substituent has no influence on the activation free energy. In an isentropic oxidation, the isokinetic temperature lies at infinite and only enthalpy of activation determines the rate. The isokinetic temperature is zero for an isoenthalpic series and the rate depends on the entropy of activation¹¹. In the present study, the existence of a linear relationship (Fig. 2, $r = 0.973$, $\sigma = 0.22$, isokinetic temperature = 299 ± 7 K) between $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ at 322 K and $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ at 315 K indicates the validity of the isokinetic relationship which suggested that the decomposition of Michaelis-Menten complex follow a common mechanism.

Fig. 2. The isokinetic plot for the oxidation of anilines by IFC in 0.8 mole fraction of acetic acid : [Substrate] = 5×10^{-2} M; [IFC] = 1×10^{-3} M; [PTS] = 2×10^{-2} M.

Since the reactions are of ion-dipolar type, it is expected that the entropy of the activated complex for all these anilines should be nearly of the same order of magnitude. However, because of difference in the polarity of

Table 3. Effect of temperature on the rate of oxidation of anilines by IFC in 0.8 mole fraction of acetic acid in water and the activation parameters for the oxidation

X	Rate constants $10^5 k$ (s ⁻¹)				E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger
	299	307	315	322 K				
H	219	472	598	2150	59	56	103	87.7
<i>p</i> -Me	591	987	3022	3204	52	49	120	85.1
<i>p</i> -OMe	37	384	1583	6543	74	138	-163	89.9
<i>p</i> -COMe	6	54	73	87	72	70	85	94.9
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	554	790	970	12000	78	77	22	83.1
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	2	4	5	6	31	29	236	99.6
<i>p</i> -Cl	288	636	748 ⁱ	1870	48	46	137	86.9
<i>p</i> -Br	180	358	468	1880	61	59	99	88.3
<i>p</i> -F	457	964	1034	2100	39	37	165	85.9
<i>m</i> -Me	478	555	1473	2401	48	46	133	86.2
<i>m</i> -COOH	7	25	48	98	73	71	82	95.6
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	6	9	22	69	70	68	97	96.9
<i>m</i> -Et	58	172	394	559	64	62	96	90.4
<i>m</i> -OMe	350	933	2564	4514	72	70	53	85.9
<i>m</i> -COMe	6	83	227	250	70	99	-17	94.1

[Substrate] = 5×10^{-2} M; [IFC] = 1×10^{-3} M; [PTS] = 2×10^{-2} M; E_a in kJ mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS^\ddagger in J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol⁻¹.

X - Substituent in aniline moiety.

different anilines, the extent of solvation should be different and hence the experimental value of ΔS^\ddagger may be different for different anilines, as observed by us in the present study.

The activation energies and the entropies and enthalpies of activation for the decomposition of the Michaelis-Menten complex were also calculated for the unsubstituted aniline in the different mole fractions of acetic acid (Table 4). The existence of a linear relationship ($r = 0.985$, $\sigma = 0.15$) between $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ at 322 K and $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ at 315 K (Fig. not shown) indicates that a single mechanism is operating in all the solvent systems studied. A perusal of data indicates that values of ΔS^\ddagger vary from -70 to $-165 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which clearly suggests that the extent of solvation of the activated complex is different in different solvent compositions. Further, the results suggested

due to an increase in solvation during the activation process. The results in Table 4 show that the largest k values are obtained in the less polar solvent mixture correspond to the decrease in activation entropy. This observation can be rationalized because polar mixtures will have some structure corresponding to the orientation of the dipolar solvent molecules due to intermolecular solvent-solvent interactions. In less polar mixtures, however, which have only a small or no dipole moment, the solvent molecules will be relatively un-oriented and consequently have higher entropy. Thus, less-polar mixtures will have a greater entropy loss as a result of increased solvation during activation process. Hence, it is presumed that, in the present study, solvent-solvent interactions play a significant role, in addition to, solute-solvent interactions in governing the rate of the reaction¹².

Table 4. Effect of temperature on the oxidation of aniline by IFC in different mole fractions of acetic acid in water and the activation parameters

m.f. of AcOH	Rate constants $10^4 k \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$				E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger
	299	307	315	322 K				
0	2	6	12	28	74	72	70	93
0.1	11	14	23	29	28	26	212	90
0.2	14	84	247	248	80	78	31	87
0.3	53	107	445	613	73	71	48	85
0.4	67	142	828	958	81	79	19	84
0.5	105	510	861	1507	71	69	46	83
0.6	239	554	949	2073	58	56	84	82
0.7	915	1009	1390	2953	32	30	165	79

[Substrate] = $5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$; [IFC] = $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; [PTS] = $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$.
 E_a in $\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$; ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$; ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} .

that the entropy of activation depends on the nature of the substituents and the composition of the solvent. This may be due to the fact that the solvation depends on various factors like the cavity produced by the dissolved molecule in the solvent, the orientation of the solvent molecules and the unspecific and specific intermolecular forces. Hence, the magnitude of ΔS^\ddagger may be due to the combination of one or more factors mentioned.

A solvent change from neat water to 0.9 mole fraction of AcOH in water causes rate acceleration for the reaction which corresponds to a decrease in ΔG^\ddagger of 14 kJ mol^{-1} . This decrease in ΔG^\ddagger indicates that the activated complex is solvated extensively by the solvent mixture. Negative entropy of activation indicates a greater degree of ordering in the transition state than in the initial state,

Structure-reactivity correlation : The decomposition of the Michaelis-Menten complexes of the listed 15 *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines was analyzed in terms of the Hammett equation. The usual Hammett equation and the modified equations failed to correlate the variation in rate of oxidation. All the dual substituent parameter (DSP) equations including the Swain *et al.* equation^{13,14} also failed to account for the variation of the rate with the substituent. The possible reason for the lack of any Linear Free Energy Relationship is that the isokinetic temperature falls within the experimental temperature. It is pertinent to note that the compensation law may lead to artifact¹⁵.

Solvent-reactivity correlation : The reaction has been studied in varying mole fractions of acetic acid in water

with a range of *ca.* 43 units of relative permittivity. The correlation of the rate constants for the decomposition of the Michaelis-Menten complexes with inverse of relative permittivity through Laidler-Eyring¹⁶ equation (average explained variance, $100 r^2$, is 88%) and with Grunwald-Winstein¹⁷ solvent ionizing power, Y , (average explained variance is 85%) does not yield any meaningful equation. These observations reveal the operation of selective or preferential solvation which includes both non-specific solute-solvent association caused by dielectric enrichment in the solvent shell of solute ions or dipolar solute molecules and specific solute-solvent association such as hydrogen bonding or EPD/EPA interactions.

In order to obtain a deeper insight into the various solvent-solvent-solute interactions, which influence reactivity, we have tried to adopt the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet and Taft¹⁸. This method may be used to unravel, quantify, correlate and rationalize multiple interacting solvent effects on reactivity. The kinetic data were correlated with the solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* characteristic of the different solvents in the form of the following LSER.

$$\log k = A_0 + s\pi^* + a\alpha + b\beta$$

where π^* is an index of solvent dipolarity/polarizability, which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent HBD (hydrogen bond donor) acidity, β is the solvent HBA (hydrogen bond acceptor) basicity of the solvent in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond and A_0 is the regression value of the solute property in the reference solvent cyclohexane. The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k$ to the indicated solvent parameter. The solvatochromic parameters employed in the present study were from the literature¹⁹. The rates of the decomposition of the Michaelis-Menten complexes studies show an excellent correlation with solvent via the above LSER with an explained variance of *ca.* 97%. Such an excellent correlation indicates the existence of both specific and non-specific solute-solvent-solvent interactions in the present study.

From the values of the regression coefficients the contribution of each parameter, on a percentage basis, to reactivity were calculated. The observation of this systematic multiple regression analysis leads us to the following conclusions. (i) The rate of the reaction is strongly influenced by specific solute-solvent interactions as indicated by the percentage contributions of α and β param-

eters. These two parameters alone accounts for about 80% of the observed solvent effect. (ii) Results indicate that the contribution of HBA basicity (represented by β term) to the total solvent effect was found to be predominant. Majority of the sign of the coefficients of this term is positive indicating better solvation of the transition state compared to the reactants. Though water and acetic acid are amphiprotic solvents, AcOH is protogenic i.e. a weaker base than water¹². It was well established that there must be a parallelism among three neat solvent properties i.e. cation-solvating tendency, HBA basicity and nucleophilicity¹². Hence increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture decreases the basicity of the medium. Thus, increase in rate with increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture suggests that the transition state is less cationic in nature when compared to the reactants and such a transition state will be stabilized by a medium with a lesser basicity. (iii) The rate of the reaction is also influenced, to an appreciable extent, by π^* which is a measure of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect. The negative sign of the coefficients of this term suggests that with decrease in polarizability/dipolarity of the medium, the rate of the oxidation process will increase and hence an increase in rate of the reaction with increase in mole fraction of acetic acid in the medium is observed in the present investigation. This observation together with the parallelism between rate increase and decrease in the solvent basicity suggests that specific solvation and stabilization of the transition state by the solvent mixture play a dominant role in the reaction. Very likely, formation of a less polar (less cationic in nature) complex between the reactants in a rapid pre-equilibrium step precedes the rate-controlling step¹².

Alternatively, water-acetic acid mixture is classified, by Blandamer and Burgess²⁰ on the basis of thermodynamic properties particularly their molar excess functions X^E , as a typically non-aqueous positive (TNAP) mixture for which G^E is positive. Further, an extra thermodynamic analysis indicates that, at least qualitatively, if G^E is positive the solute should be more soluble in the mixture than predicted from the solubilities in the two pure solvents. Hence, in the present study, it is presumed that the increase in rate, with increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture, may be due to the fact that the transition state is more hydrophobic than the initial state and such a transition state will be stabilized in a TNAP solvent mixture consequently enhancing the rate of the reaction.

Mechanism :

IFC is an anionic condensed form of chromic acid. In aqueous and partly aqueous media, chromate is hydrolyzed and in acidic solution the speciation of Cr^{VI} are FCrO_3^- , HFCrO_3 and $\text{H}_2\text{FCrO}_3^+$. A thorough study on the abundance of various Cr^{VI} species are available in literature which reveal that the most abundant Cr^{VI} species in the reaction solution is halochromic acid²¹⁻²³.

The oxidations are first order in IFC and increases with increase in acid concentration. The Michaelis-Menten dependence of the oxidation rates on [substrate] confirms the formation of complexes in a rapid pre-equilibrium. Experiments reveal involvement of Cr^{IV} intermediate in the oxidation of anilines by Cr^{VI} reagent. Mn^{II} ion suppresses the oxidation rates. Manganese(II) ion reduces Cr^{IV} to Cr^{III} . In the absence of Mn^{II} ion, Cr^{IV} formed reduces Cr^{VI} to Cr^{V} . The oxidation of aniline by Cr^{V} is fast^{21,22}.

mental findings, viz. the first order reaction each in IFC and acid and the Michaelis-Menten dependence of the rate on [Substrate]. The products separated suggest the formation of phenylhydroxylamine, indicating N attack otherwise azobenzene formation would not have been possible²⁴. Formation of azobenzene from phenylhydroxylamine follows Scheme 2.

Having decided the site of the attack, the next point which requires consideration is the manner of electron transfer. Conflicting ideas have been prevailing as to the true mechanism operative in halochromate oxidations^{23,25}. The two mechanisms proposed are (i) direct hydride ion loss in a concerted process and (ii) prior formation of an ester in a reversible step, preceding the loss of a hydride ion. In the present study kinetics and solvent variation study and the results of the correlation of rate data with solvent parameters favors our choice of the second mecha-

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

The suggested mechanism leads to the rate law

$$\frac{-d [\text{Oxidizing agent}]}{dt} = \frac{Kk [\text{Substrate}] [\text{HFCrO}_3]}{(1 + K [\text{Substrate}])}$$

The above rate law is in agreement with all the experi-

nism i.e. reversible formation of an ester (very likely concerted transfer of oxygen from HFCrO_3 to N-atom and electron pair from N-atom to Cr^{VI} leading to the formation of a complex which is less cationic in nature) preceding the H^- loss.

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